

A DYNAMIC MODELLING APPROACH TO SIMULATE THE RANGE EXPANSION OF THE EUROPEAN STARLING

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SYNOPSIS

- The European Starling (ES), *Sturnus vulgaris*, was first introduced to South Africa in 1897.
- The ES is 1 of 3 birds on the world's worst 'invasive species' list.
- It is of great theoretical and management value to elucidate the invasion process and identify key environmental and physiological drivers of the range dynamics, which allow us to further forecast their future distributions.

AIMS

- Design a dynamical model that closely resembles the invasion process of ES in SA.
- Incorporate a variety of environmental and biological characteristics into the model, including: growth, mortality, carrying capacity, dispersal kernel, elevation barriers, suitable habitat, human population density, individual memory and genetic variation.
- Study the influence that each of the above mentioned factors has on ES range expansion.

METHODS

I. NICHE MODELLING

A correlative species distribution model (SDM) studies the relationship between species' occurrences and environmental variables to define the species' potential distribution. The SDM method used for this study was MaxEnt [1].

Environmental variables used and their relative contribution to the MaxEnt model:

- Precipitation of coldest quarter (66.7%)
- Landcover (27%)
- Precipitation of warmest quarter (5.7%)
- Max temp. of warmest month (0.5%)

II. INDIVIDUAL BASED MODELLING

An individual based model (IBM) is a computational model which simulates the actions and interactions of individuals within a population across space and time (t , in years).

RESULTS

t=20

Population Abundance

t=60

t=100

SABAP1, 1997
South African Bird Atlas Project

DISCUSSION

The hybrid method designed here highlights the importance of incorporating population demography, physiological constraints and environmental characteristics to explain the geographic range structure of non-native species.

ADDITIONAL RESEARCH

- Explore the effects of spatial sorting processes on range expansion.
- Explore the changes of life-history strategies on model dynamics.
- Develop an IBM framework that can be applied to other mobile invasive species.

REFERENCES

- [1] Phillips, S.J. et al. 2006. *Maximum entropy modelling of species geographic distributions*. Ecological Modelling. 190:231-259.
 [2] Hui, C. et al. 2012. *Flexible dispersal strategies in native and non-native ranges: environmental quality and the 'good-stay, bad-disperse' rule*. Ecography. 35:1024-1032.

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